

CHEMICAL-THERMAL-AND MECHANICAL MODELING APPROACH OF A THERMOSETTING MATRICE CURE

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1 INTRODUCTION

In the industry, in particular the naval one, the use of composites ensuring structural functions is getting more and more important today. The optimization of these structures becomes inevitable and requires a very precise knowledge of the characteristics of the material and its internal state at the end of the manufacturing process. More particularly, during the cure of the composite, internal stresses are generated and several imperfections (bubbles, fibers wavinesses...) may appear, consequently decreasing mechanical performances of the final material. These phenomena are taken a consequent aspect in the manufacture of thick composites with long fibers, since at the end of the operation of cure the presence of fibers regularly corrugated within the plies can be observed. In thin composites it seems that this phenomenon is also active as suggested by the works of Paluch (1994) for the case of long carbon fibers. This author clearly showed that at the end of cure, fibers are presented in an undulatory form. Jochum (1999) proposed an explanation of this phenomenon : during the thermosetting reaction of the resin, the volume shrinkage associated to the phase change from the initial liquid state to the solid state induces a compressive loading onto the fiber which is destabilized and is therefore subjected to a buckle instability (microbuckling phenomenon). Internal stresses generating these defects during the cure of a composite matrix result from a complex process where *thermal*, *physicochemical* and *mechanical* phenomena are mixed. This complexity is in addition exacerbated by the both thermo activated and exothermal behavior of the thermosetting chemical reaction of the resin. Moreover throughout the cure, mechanical characteristics are evolving with the temperature and the degree of conversion of the chemical reaction.

The construction of simulation tools for the process of cure requires the development of coupling models for the taken into account of the mechanics, the thermal, the diffusion and the chemistry. From a theoretical point of view, the four aspects of the problem were generally approached separately. Models of coupling between the thermal and the chemical kinetics exist (Chachad (1996), Roux et al (1998)). Some works of modeling of the pultrusion process can be observed and the authors approached in a consequent way these couplings (Joshi et Al, (1999)). Tools by accurate finite elements made their appearance (Sunil et Al, (2001)). However these tools are established on formulations where all the couplings were not envisaged. Moreover the chemical reaction is generally approached as a scalar relation covering the degree of conversion only. But works on chemical reactions (Sadi, (1990)) showed that according to the initial mixture of the component parts, the chemical reaction kinetics vary, and the initial heterogeneities of the fractions of the components induce diffusion of the different elements. These phenomena strongly influence the characteristics of

the matter all over the cure, as well as at the end of it. The modeling of these phenomena coupled with the temperature and with the mechanics seems to be never having been approached.

The objective of this work is to build up a first modeling approach taking into account the couplings. As prospects for this work we wish to develop numerical predictive tools, being able to quantify residual stresses, inside chemical state of the material and its consequences on the quality of the obtained material.

In this paper, a first simple model is detailed. It is built within the framework of the generalized standard mediums which interest is to allow the basis of a modeling describing all the couplings between mechanical, thermal, diffusive and chemical aspects in the context of linear viscoelasticity.

2 MODELING APPROACH PRESENTATION

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The system is supposed being a traditional continuous medium, made up with a mixture of hardener, accelerator and resin. All macroscopic representative elementary volume (REV) is considered homogeneous and opened and is characterized by averaged physical units defining the mixture. Thus, we are involved here in its averaged behavior. The diffusion of each "species" is a molecular diffusion following a Fick law type. It is controlled by the gradients of concentration or mass ratio of the various species. In this REV the various elements react between them to create the matrix. This evolution of the mixture, governed by the equations of the diffusion and the equations of the chemistry, is taken into account in the equations of the thermal and of the mechanics.

2.1 MASS BALANCE

By noting ρ_0 the initial density, Y_i the mass fraction of each species (accelerator, hardener, matrix obtained), M_i the current molar mass of the species i and \vec{J}_{m_i} the associated mass current, ν_{ir} the stoichiometric coefficient of the component part i for the reaction r , w_r the reaction rate for the reaction r , the mass balance of the component part i which leads to the equation of distribution of the corresponding species is then :

$$\rho \frac{dY_i}{dt} = \sum_r \nu_{ir} M_i w_r - \text{div} (\vec{J}_{m_i}) \quad (1)$$

In this result, we have neglected the accelerator mass ratio which is very low in comparison with other current species. On the other hand, his effect is reintroduced in the evolution rate of the chemical reaction. Moreover the writing of the total mass conservation in the REV leads us to a relation between mass ratio of the resin and of the hardener which is written as following :

$$Y_m + Y_r + Y_d = 1 \quad (2)$$

This relation is used in the formalism to simplify the expressions.

2.2 MECHANICAL BALANCE

The mechanical balance leads to the equation of movement (3) where $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}$ denotes the Cauchy stress tensor and \vec{f} denotes the mass density of forces applied onto the REV.

$$\vec{\text{div}} \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \rho \vec{f} = \vec{0} \quad (3)$$

2.3 THERMO DYNAMICAL BALANCE, FIRST AND SECOND PRINCIPLE

• STATE LAWS

Classically in thermodynamics of continuous mediums, the specific free energy potential is introduced to carry out state laws. From a constitutive law point of view, a Kelvin-Voigt model was considered. It is the minimal model to represent a viscous behavior for a polymer. It is clear that it is not enough to predict the mixture mechanical behavior evolution during the cure. However by taking into account indirect couplings (temperature and degree of cure dependency for mechanical characteristics) it should be accurate enough, while limiting the implementation work in a finite element industrial code.

By using a decomposition of the strain into an elastic part (reversible) and an inelastic (non reversible) part like $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}} = \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e + \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v$, this potential is a function of the temperature T , of elastic part of the strain $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e$, of viscoelastic part of the strain $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v$ and of the mass fractions Y_i of each component.

This mechanical model suppose a stress partition $\underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\text{an}} + \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\text{vr}}$, containing an inelastic part and a viscous reversible part, and also a strain partition $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}} = \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e + \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v$ into an elastic and viscous part. In this particular framework, the material state is defined by following variables : temperature T , elastic and viscous strains, $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e$, $\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v$, resin and hardener mass ratios Y_r and Y_d . State laws are classically established with a specific free energy potential $\psi = \psi(T, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_r, Y_d)$, and by assuming of a normal parametric :

$$\cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} = \rho \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e} \right)_{T, Y_d, Y_r}, \quad \cdot s = - \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial T} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, Y_d, Y_r}, \quad \cdot \mu_i = \left(\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial Y_i} \right)_{T, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, Y_{k \neq i}} \quad (4)$$

$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial} \right)_*$ denotes partial derivative with * constant.

By considering the framework of small perturbations, i.e. infinitesimal strains and few thermal and mass variations, the second order development of potential ψ allows to build linear behavior laws as following :

$$\begin{aligned} \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} &= \underline{\underline{\sigma}}_0 + \lambda^0 (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e) \underline{\underline{I}} + 2\mu^0 \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e - (3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0) \alpha_T^0 (T - T_0) \underline{\underline{I}} \\ &\quad - (3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0) \alpha_{\text{dm}}^0 (Y_d - Y_d^0) \underline{\underline{I}} - (3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0) \alpha_{\text{rm}}^0 (Y_r - Y_r^0) \underline{\underline{I}} \\ \cdot s &= s_0 + \frac{C_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_m, Y_d, Y_r}}{T_0} (T - T_0) + \frac{(3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0) \alpha_T^0}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e) + \frac{(3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty) \alpha_T^\infty}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v) \\ \cdot \mu_a &= \mu_m^0 - D_{\text{md}} (Y_d - Y_d^0) - D_{\text{mr}} (Y_r - Y_r^0) - \frac{(3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0) \alpha_m^0}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e) - \frac{(3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty) \alpha_m^\infty}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\bullet \mu_d &= \mu_d^0 + D_{dm}(Y_d - Y_d^0) + D_{dmr}(Y_r - Y_r^0) - \frac{(3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0)\alpha_d^0}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e) - \frac{(3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty)\alpha_d^\infty}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v) \\
\bullet \mu_r &= \mu_r^0 + D_{rm}(Y_d - Y_d^0) + D_{rmr}(Y_r - Y_r^0) - \frac{(3\lambda^0 + 2\mu^0)\alpha_r^0}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e) - \frac{(3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty)\alpha_r^\infty}{\rho} (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v) \\
\bullet \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{vr} &= \underline{\underline{\sigma}}_o^{vr} + \lambda^0 (\text{tr} \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v) \underline{\underline{I}} + 2\mu^0 \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v - (3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty)\alpha_r^\infty (T - T_o) \underline{\underline{I}} \\
&\quad - (3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty)\alpha_{dm}^\infty (Y_d - Y_d^0)\underline{\underline{I}} - (3\lambda^\infty + 2\mu^\infty)\alpha_{rm}^\infty (Y_r - Y_r^0)\underline{\underline{I}}
\end{aligned}$$

where T_o , Y_i^0 , $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}_o$, s_o and μ_i^0 denote respectively temperature, mass ratio of species i , stress tensor, specific entropy and strain free initial chemical potential for no thermal and no mass gap, $\underline{\underline{C}}$ denotes elastic modulus tensor. $\rho C_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_d, Y_r}$ is the specific heat at constant strain and mass ratios, $\underline{\underline{k}}$ is the tensor of thermal coefficient of expansion and D_{ij} , D_{ijk} , $\underline{\underline{C}}_i$, α_{dm}^∞ , α_{rm}^∞ , α_i^∞ , α_i^0 are coefficients indicating couplings effects between thermodynamical forces and state variables.

In the definition of the chemical potentials, terms which are in product with strain trace appear naturally when the shrinkage generated by the crosslinking reaction is taken in consideration. By the way, the Kelvin-Voigt model allows to consider both instantaneous and long time coupling effects.

• HEAT EQUATION

By noting \vec{J}_q the heat flow, r the external sources of heat (radiation), $C_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_d, Y_r}$ the specific heat at constant strains and mass ratio, the equation of heat containing all the couplings in linear viscoelasticity can then be written under following expression :

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho C_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_d, Y_r} \frac{dT}{dt} &= - \text{div} \vec{J}_q + r + \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v : \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{an} \\
&\quad + T \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\sigma}}}{\partial T} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_d, Y_r} : \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e + \left(\frac{\partial \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{vr}}{\partial T} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v, Y_d, Y_r} : \underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^v \right\} \\
&\quad + \rho \left\{ T \left(\frac{\partial (\mu_d - \mu_m)}{\partial T} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, Y_d, Y_r} - (\mu_d - \mu_m) \right\} \dot{Y}_d \\
&\quad + \rho \left\{ T \left(\frac{\partial (\mu_r - \mu_m)}{\partial T} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}^e, Y_d, Y_r} - (\mu_r - \mu_m) \right\} \dot{Y}_r.
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The two last terms of the equality correspond to the heat created by the diffusion of the components within the mixture and by the progress of the chemical reaction. The others terms are classic one in thermo-viscous-elasticity.

• DISSIPATIONS

The second principle of the thermodynamic allows the definition of the volume dissipation φ (positive or null) related to the production of entropy.

$$\varphi = \varphi_1 + \varphi_2 + \varphi_3 + \varphi_4 \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

This dissipation can be broken up into four contributions of distinct origins according to (8) : φ_1 is the intrinsic or mechanical dissipative contribution, φ_2 , φ_3 , φ_4 are the contributions respectively related to temperature variation, degree of conversion of the reactions and gradient of chemical potential. Corresponding expressions are as following :

$$\varphi_1 = \underline{\underline{\sigma}} : \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^v ; \quad \varphi_2 = - \vec{J}_s \cdot \text{grad } T ; \quad \varphi_3 = \sum_r \mathbf{A}_r w_r ; \quad \varphi_4 = - \sum_{i=a,d,r} \vec{J}_{m_i} \cdot \text{grad } \mu_i \quad (8)$$

with $\vec{J}_s = \frac{1}{T} [\vec{J}_q - \sum_{i=a,d,r} \mu_i \vec{J}_{m_i}]$ the leaving current of entropy.

The respect of the second principle leads to define a potential of dissipation \mathbf{d} and its dual \mathbf{d}^* (9) by the help of a Legendre-Fenchel transformation. According to the desired assumptions of decoupling, these scalar values functions, continuous, convex and positive, will have different expressions. In the case of a total coupling between dissipative phenomena, the dual potential seems therefore like a single function, given by equation (9). Under the assumption of normal dissipativity, specific to the standard mediums, complementary laws of evolution indicated at equations (11) are classically established like following, where A_r denotes the De Donder affinity.

$$\mathbf{d}^* = \mathbf{d}^* (\underline{\underline{\sigma}}, - \text{grad } T, - \text{grad } \mu_i, \mathbf{A}_r) \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \cdot \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^v &= \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{d}^*}{\partial \underline{\underline{\sigma}}} \right)_{-\text{grad } T, -\text{grad } \mu_i, \mathbf{A}_r} \\ \cdot \vec{J}_s &= \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{d}^*}{\partial [-\text{grad } T]} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}, -\text{grad } \mu_i, \mathbf{A}_r} \\ \cdot \vec{J}_{m_i} &= \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{d}^*}{\partial [-\text{grad } \mu_i]} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}, -\text{grad } T, -\text{grad } \mu_{k \neq i}, \mathbf{A}_r} \\ \cdot w_r &= \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{d}^*}{\partial \mathbf{A}_r} \right)_{\underline{\underline{\sigma}}, -\text{grad } T, -\text{grad } \mu_i} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Moreover if dissipation phenomena are supposed being governed by linear laws (small perturbations) and by the assumption of the validity of the Curie principle, the potential \mathbf{d}^* is under a quadratic uncoupled form and evolution laws are :

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\underline{\underline{\varepsilon}}}^v &= \underline{\underline{k}}_\sigma : \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\text{an}} = \frac{1 + \nu^v}{E^v} \underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\text{an}} - \frac{\nu^v}{E^v} \text{tr}(\underline{\underline{\sigma}}^{\text{an}}) \underline{\underline{I}} \\ \vec{J}_s &= \underline{\underline{k}}_T [-\text{grad } T] \\ \vec{J}_{m_d} &= - \underline{\underline{k}}_{\mu_{md}} [\text{grad}(\mu_d - \mu_m)] - c_{\mu_{mr} \mu_{md}} \cdot [\text{grad}(\mu_r - \mu_m)] \\ \vec{J}_{m_r} &= - \underline{\underline{k}}_{\mu_{mr}} [\text{grad}(\mu_r - \mu_m)] - c_{\mu_{mr} \mu_{md}} \cdot [\text{grad}(\mu_d - \mu_m)] \\ w_r &= k_{A_r}(\mathbf{A}_r) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The second expression corresponds to the Fourier relation for the simple case of conduction. The third and fourth equation are reduced to : $\vec{J}_{m_i} = \underline{k}_{\mu_i} [-\text{grad } \mu_i]$ and finally the last one is reduced to $w_i = k_{A_i}(A_r)$. These relations are respectively the Fick law for each component, for the simple case of diffusion, and the classical equation of the chemical kinetics.

Onsager coefficients \underline{k}_{σ} , \underline{k}_T , \underline{k}_{μ_i} , k_{A_r} and $c_{\mu_{ij} \mu_{il}}$ are the same as these classically employed in the field of the mechanics, the thermal and the diffusion. At this step of the formulation, it is easy to introduce many couplings between dissipative phenomena in a judicious way. This approach of generalized standard mediums allows to establish state laws systematically, nevertheless the taking into account of viscosity and chemical reaction degree of conversion are related to the framework of non reversible out of balance thermodynamic processes. However, since we wish to implement these laws into an industrial FEM code, we have chosen a more classical construction which is not so completely appropriate for the physical involved phenomena, but it simplifies the implementation.

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLINES

In this paper, basis of a modeling approach coupling thermal, diffusion, chemical phenomena, and the mechanics were established within the framework of the standard generalized mediums in the context of linear viscoelasticity. The next step consists to build up the specific free dissipation and potential energy by experimental identifications. This work is under progress at the E.N.S.I.E.T.A institute, namely by mean of DMA experiments. In addition to this a numerical tool coupling mechanical, physical and chemical phenomena is developed on the basis of developments presented above. The long-term objective is to build up a predictive tool, able to grasp finely all the process of cure.

RÉFÉRENCES

- Chachad et al., 1996, Thermal Model for Three-Dimensional Irregular Shaped Pultruded Fiberglass Composites, *J. Comp. Mater.*, **6**, 30.
- Jochum C., 1999, Microflambage des fibres lors de la cuisson des composites stratifiés à fibres longues, Ph.D. Thesis University of Metz, France.
- Joshi et al., 1999, A Numerical Approach to the Modelinf of Polymer Curing in Fiber-Reinforced composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **59**, pp.1003-13.
- Paluch B., 1994, Analyse des imperfections Géométriques affectant les Fibres dans un Matériau Composite à renfort Unidirectionnel, *La recherche aéronautique*, **VI**, pp. 431-448.
- Roux et al., 1998, Comparaison de measurements and modeling for pultrusion of a fiberglass/epoxy 1-beam., *J. Reinf. Plas. Comp.*, **17**, 1557-79.
- Sadi, 1990, Contribution à l'étude du comportement mécanique d'une résine époxy-amine aux jeunes ages: approche physico-chimique, Ph.D. Thesis E.N.P.C., France
- Sunil et al., 2001, Three-dimensional finite-element/nodal-control-volume simulation of the pultrusion process with temperature-dependant material properties including resin shrinkage, *Comp. Sci. Technol.*, **61**, 1539-47.